

ECOLOGICAL TREND IN CLOTHING DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The topic of ecology sets the vector of a new approach to the fashion industry. More and more designers and manufacturers are thinking about the use of natural materials and recycled textile waste from light industry. The aim of the work was to study the impact of «fast fashion» on the environment. Consideration of the direction of the «green economy» in the light industry of the new generation.

Keywords: Fashion, design, glamour, ecology, HM, Zara, Peacocks, natural resources, "Green economy."

There are different opinions on what eco-fashion is and what directions it includes. Some believe that eco-clothing is made from natural fabrics. Others hold the view that an item is ecological if it is made from recycled materials.

Fashion, design, glamour – you might wonder what ecology has to do with this. Surprisingly, the impact of the fashion industry on the environment has reached dramatic levels. This is related to the emergence of so-called fast fashion. Clothing production ranks second among the most harmful and destructive industries for the environment, right after the oil industry. "Fast fashion" is a consumption model where clothing is inexpensive but wears out quickly, thus requiring frequent wardrobe updates (retail chains such as HM, Zara, Peacocks, and Topshop).

The ecological problems associated with the fast fashion industry worldwide are well reflected in the following facts:

- According to experts, the global textile industry uses 378 billion liters of water annually.
- The consumption of Earth's natural resources is increasing due to rising energy, chemicals, and raw material consumption.
- The rapid turnover of fashion trends leads to an increase in textile waste, both from production and consumption.

- Fuel consumption in textile factories is almost directly proportional to the amount of water used by these factories.

- The negative impact of fashion on the environment does not end when clothing is unpacked at home. It continues during the usage phase (washing, ironing). The global textile industry consumes 1 trillion kilowatt-hours every year, accounting for 10 percent of the total carbon impact on the environment.

- The fashion industry uses a wide range of chemicals at various stages of creating an item and its packaging. Synthetic fibers account for 60 percent of global demand. These fibers are produced from oil – a non-renewable natural resource.

- Textile production contributes to air and freshwater pollution. The constant supply of fast fashion clothing involves widespread and regular transportation, not always using "green" transport. Cotton cultivation relies on significant freshwater consumption; producing a single t-shirt can require around 2,700 liters of water.

According to UN data, over the past 20 years, global clothing production volumes have doubled, reaching 100 million tons. As we can see from these facts, the ecological problem in this area has become so global that neither producers nor consumers can afford to ignore it any longer. A number of brands have signed the Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Action. They have committed to reducing emissions by 30% over the next 10 years and aim to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050. However, what specific steps will be taken to achieve this remains unclear. Changing behavior means, first and foremost, learning to love the surrounding world. When a person loves, they want to care for and protect the object of their love. Love should not be merely contemplative but rather actively engaged. Fashion can and should be more ecological; to create this positive effect, it is vital to rethink how design is created, how resources are extracted, how production operates, and how clothing is consumed and distributed. The ecological debt to the planet and future generations has compelled certain countries (such as South Korea) to adopt the national idea of "Green Economy." Designers are a source of inspiration for every model created, and the ethics and ecological sustainability of a product ultimately depend on them. Researchers have found that designers influence the ecological and economic costs of a product by 80-90 percent. It is essential to intensively study processes in the living world, learn from nature's accumulated experience, and widely implement this knowledge in economic practices. We need to shift our civilization's focus from a technically consumer-oriented approach to a biologically "green" one. Examples of companies implementing "Green Economy" principles include:

- The Japanese company "Teijin"
- The American brand Levi's
- The American brand Nike

As for us, ordinary consumers, what can each of us do? Certainly, we can participate in various eco-projects like "Sobiator," "Baraholka," and "Garage Sale." Through such projects, old jeans and sweaters can find a second life and help people in difficult situations. Based on the data studied, I can confidently state that we all need to make responsible choices when it comes to purchasing clothing. Rational choices will save us from ecological catastrophe.

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